

**AFLATOXIN SAFETY EVALUATION AND DETECTION OF ADULTERATION IN
LOCALLY PROCESSED POWDERED GINGER SOLD IN SELECTED MARKETS IN
KADUNA NORTH, KADUNA.**

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Abstract

Aflatoxins are potent carcinogens and remain a serious safety concern; *adulteration* compromises the nutritional and medicinal properties of spices, reducing their purity and therapeutic potential. This study evaluated the safety and authenticity of locally processed powdered ginger sold in selected markets within Kaduna North, Kaduna by determining moisture and ash contents, aflatoxin concentration, and detecting adulteration. Powdered ginger samples were collected from three markets (Kawo, Unguwar Rimi and Central) in triplicates. Control samples (peeled and unpeeled) were prepared by collecting the raw samples of ginger. Moisture and ash contents were determined using AOAC standard procedures, aflatoxin concentration were analyzed using Enzyme linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA). Attenuated Total Reflectance-Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) was used in the spectral range of 4000-650 cm^{-1} to detect adulteration. Moisture content ranged from 3.82-5.21%, with the highest value recorded in Kawo market and the lowest in the peeled control. Ash content ranged from 4.27-4.89%, with the peeled control having the highest value indicating better mineral composition. Aflatoxin concentrations ranged from 0.153-0.274 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$. Notably, despite the presence of aflatoxins, all samples remained well below the regulatory limit of 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$. FTIR spectral analysis revealed compositional differences between the market-processed and control samples. Additional peak shifts in the fingerprint region (1500–500 cm^{-1}) further supported adulteration, confirming similarities between the market-processed ginger and the tested adulterants. These analyses proved effective in detecting contamination and adulteration, prompting the need for regular monitoring and quality control of spice products.

Keywords: Aflatoxin, Adulteration, ELISA, FTIR, Ginger

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

Ginger (*Zingiber officinale*) is a flowering plant that grows underground, where its rhizome known as ginger root or simply ginger is widely used both as a spice and in traditional medicine (Iqbal *et al.*, 2024). Ginger is popular around the world, with its demand remaining strong throughout history. They hold significant economic importance due to their diverse functions, such as imparting taste, colour, aroma, preservative qualities, and medicinal properties (Negi *et al.*, 2021). Beyond enhancing flavor, clinical investigation of ginger shows different medicinal uses as analgesic, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antithrombotic, antidiabetic and antihypertensive, and in the treatment of nausea, vomiting, and other digestive disorders (Abdo *et al.*, 2020).

The issue of post-harvest losses in spices is substantial (Alice *et al.*, 2016) and concerns over the risks of contamination and adulteration are growing. Pre-harvest factors, such as pest and insect infestations, can introduce fungi into spices, contributing to contamination (Cinar and Onbasi, 2019). Among fungi, *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium*, *Fusarium* and *Alternata* are the filamentous fungi which are common contaminants and under favorable conditions (high humidity and high temperature), they multiply on different products where they produced mycotoxins (Mustafa *et al.*, 2024). *Aspergillus* species, known as storage fungi, are of particular concern as they can survive at very low water activity and produce harmful

mycotoxins during prolonged storage. Among the mycotoxins, aflatoxins (AFs) are the most prevalent in spices, typically produced by *Aspergillus* spp. (Syamilah *et al.*, 2022). Specific aflatoxins, including AFB1, AFB2, AFG1, and AFG2, are especially dangerous, with AFB1 classified as a Group 1 carcinogen due to its high toxicity (Wakhungu *et al.*, 2021). Almost 70% population of the world are exposed to the threats of aflatoxins, including 4.5 billion people living in Asia and Africa, highlighting the importance of monitoring aflatoxin and mycotoxin levels in food products to prevent toxicoses (Bunny *et al.*, 2024). Health issues associated with mycotoxin exposure include allergic reactions, metabolic and biochemical disruptions, reproductive health problems, fetal development issues, immune disorders, and in severe cases, death (Wakhungu *et al.*, 2021). Detecting aflatoxins is essential to prevent the health risks associated with these mycotoxins and to ensure the safety of spice products. Reduction of mycotoxin contamination can be achieved by several processes including cleaning, milling, and hulling of grains (Makundi *et al.*, 2024).

Adulteration in spices reduces their natural composition and quality by adding foreign substances or removing essential elements. Frequently, old or spoiled spices are blended with fresh batches to increase volume, ultimately boosting profit at the expense of quality (Pantola and Agarwa, 2021). As the spice industry continues to expand

economically, these products have increasingly become targets for adulteration. A contributing factor to food adulteration is the inadequate regulation and enforcement of food safety standards. In many countries, food laws are either weak or poorly enforced due to understaffed, untrained, or corrupt regulatory agencies (Haji *et al.*, 2023). This lack of oversight allows dishonest businesses to engage in food adulteration without consequences. Additionally, outsourcing food production to countries with lower labor costs has exacerbated the problem, as reduced production expenses and high profit margins have encouraged adulteration and counterfeit practices (Choudhary *et al.*, 2020). Common adulteration practices include the addition of inexpensive sub-products derived from various food sources, such as wheat, corn, potatoes, and other tubers (Sezer *et al.*, 2018). Spice adulteration poses a significant issue, increasing product impurity and compromising consumer safety. The increasing incidence of food fraud has become a significant global health concern, necessitating comprehensive techniques to detect adulteration in spices. Identifying adulteration in spices is challenging and typically demands the application of advanced analytical methods (Wadood *et al.*, 2020). Spectrometric techniques, despite varying in chemical content due to natural or adulterated compositions, are effective for identifying unique spectroscopic fingerprints that facilitate adulteration detection (de Macêdo *et al.*, 2021). Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy

is among the most used techniques for detecting food fraud. It is rapid, simple, non-destructive, and cost-effective (Haji *et al.*, 2023)

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study Area

The study was conducted in Kaduna North, Kaduna State, Nigeria, which is located at latitude 10°35'N and longitude 7°25'E. Kaduna North is situated in the northern part of Kaduna State, covering an area of approximately 70.20 km², with a population of 364,575 as of 2006 Nigeria population census and a projection of 538,600 as at 2022 (City Population, 2020). The city's economy is driven by a diverse range of activities, including trade, small-scale industries, manufacturing and food processing, particularly grinding and packaging highlights its role as a key distribution hub for both retail and wholesale transactions.

2.2 Sample Collection

Samples of processed powdered ginger were collected from three (3) different markets in triplicates from different vendors from Kaduna North (Kawo market, Unguwar Rimi market and Central market). Raw samples of ginger and possible adulterants (Maize flour and alligator pepper) were also sourced. All collected samples were transported in clean, airtight containers to prevent contamination and stored at room temperature before further processing and analysis.

2.3 Sample Preparation

The individual samples for each processed powdered ginger were thoroughly mixed to form a composite sample for each market. The raw ginger samples which serve as the controls were processed in two forms; with their peels intact and without their peels before being cut into smaller pieces, sun dried and grounded into powdered form. All prepared samples were stored in airtight containers (Amposah *et al.*, 2022).

2.4 Moisture Content Determination

This was carried out following gravimetric method, according to the procedure of Association of Official Analytical Chemist - A.O.A.C (Akoji *et al.*, 2022). A washed and dried crucible was weighed as (w_1), 2g of the sample was then added and weighed as (w_2) and recorded. It was then placed in an oven set at 105°C for 3hrs and weighed again as (w_3) and recorded (Akoji *et al.*, 2022).

The percentage amount of moisture resulting from the drying was calculated using:

$$\% \text{ Moisture Content} = \frac{(w_2 - w_3)}{(w_2 - w_1)} \times 100 \quad \text{equation 1}$$

2.5 Total Ash Content Determination

This was carried out following the incineration method, according to the procedure of Association of Official Analytical Chemist - A.O.A.C (Akoji *et al.*, 2022). A Platinum dish washed, dried and cooled was weighed as (w_1), 3g of the sample was added and weighed as (w_2) and recorded. It was then transferred using a pair

of tong into a muffle furnace and heated at 550°C until it fully ashes (color changes to gray) and the weight (w_3) was recorded after cooling to a room temperature (Akoji *et al.*, 2022). The percentage ash content was calculated using:

$$\% \text{ Ash Content} = \frac{(w_2 - w_3)}{(w_2 - w_1)} \times 100 \quad \text{equation 2}$$

2.6 Total Aflatoxin Determination

Enzyme linked immunosorbent assay ELISA (Ridascreen Aflatoxin Total Art. No. R4701) test kit was used for aflatoxin determination in the samples. This method relies on antibodies that specifically target the compounds of interest and operates through an enzyme-linked colour reaction (Miklós *et al.*, 2020).

2.6.1 Sample Extraction

Sample extraction was performed according to the manufacturer's instruction (Ridascreen Aflatoxin Total Art. No. R4701). 10ml of 70/30 (v/v) methanol-water extraction solvent was added to 2grams of each ground spice sample and the solution was extracted by shaking for 10 minutes using orbital shaker. The sample was then allowed to settle, and the top layer of extract was filtered through a Whatman No. 1 filter paper and the filtrate was collected into the test tube, 100 µL of filtrate was transferred into a different test tube and was diluted into a test tube containing 600 µL of distilled water (Haruna *et al.*, 2017).

2.6.2 ELISA TEST

This was done according to Ridascreen Aflatoxin Total Art. No. R4701 test kit manual.

50 μL of each standard and sample was added into each microwell. 50 μL of conjugate was added first to each well, then 50 μL of antibody was added into each well and was carefully mixed by shaking the plate manually and then it was incubated for 30 minutes at room temperature (20-25°C). The contents of the microwell strips were discarded followed by washing each microwell by filling it with 250 μL wash buffer and then dumping the water from the microwell strips. Microwell strips were then tapped using absorbent (tissue) paper by holding it upside down to expel as much residual water as possible. The bottom of the microwells was then dried with a dry towel. 100 μL of the substrate/chromogen was added into each microwell and was mixed gently by shaking the plate manually before incubation at room temperature for 15 minutes and a blue colour developed. 100 μL of stop solution was added into each microwell strip, and then there was colour change from blue to yellow. The strips were then read with microwell reader using an absorbance filter of 450 nm (Haruna *et al.*, 2017).

2.7 Detection of Adulteration

2.7.1 Physical characteristics

Physical parameters assessed included odour, colour, texture and appearance (Amponsah *et al.*, 2022).

2.7.2 FTIR Data Acquisition

All spectra of the selected samples were measured using ATR-FTIR (Agilent Cary 630

FTIR Spectrometer, Australia). Isopropanol was used to clean the crystal before collecting the background. All spectra were recorded in the transmittance mode. The transmission technique was applied to conduct 8 sample scans and 8 background scans for each of the sample in the spectral range of 4000-650 cm^{-1} . Samples to be analyzed were placed directly on the diamond crystal of ATR-FTIR. The selected spectral range covers the characteristic absorption bands relevant to the compounds of interest, ensuring detailed and informative spectral data (Madhuri *et al.*, 2021). The control samples were used to establish reference FTIR spectral markers for ginger. Possible adulterants (Maize flour and alligator pepper) were also analyzed to establish their spectral characteristics. After establishing the spectral markers from the control samples and possible adulterants, the FTIR spectra of the market-processed samples were compared with these reference markers.

2.8 Data Analysis

The data obtained was subjected to appropriate statistical analysis using SPSS version 25. Inferential (ANOVA) and descriptive analysis (mean and standard deviation) were employed. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test for significance at $p < 0.01$.

3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Percentage Moisture and Ash Content

The overall percentage moisture content ranged

from 3.82-5.21%. The highest percentage was recorded for Kawo market at 5.21% while the lowest was recorded for the peeled control at 3.82% as shown in Table 1.

Moisture analysis provides insights into the nutritional value, shelf life, digestibility, and technological efficiency of food products (Popescu *et al.*, 2022). The difference in moisture content could be attributed to environmental exposure, storage conditions and processing variations. The moisture content recorded in the market-processed samples being higher than the controls could be attributed to environmental exposure, poor storage conditions, or possible adulteration such as starchy adulterants which tend to absorb and retain moisture and this is also in line with the work reported by Obani *et al.* (2025) who also recorded the lowest moisture content in the control emphasizing the importance of proper storage to increase the shelf life of spices. Overall, the moisture content still aligns with the result reported by Abubakar *et al.* (2019) who reported $4.26 \pm 0.1\%$, $4.74 \pm 0.3\%$ moisture in peeled and unpeeled ginger respectively. Moisture content serves as an indicator of food freshness and its potential shelf life before spoilage. Lower moisture content suggests that

the spices can be stored for extended periods without significant quality deterioration (Shehu *et al.*, 2023).

The overall total ash content ranged from 4.27-4.89% with the control (peeled) recording the highest at 4.89% and Kawo market ginger recording the lowest at 4.27% as shown in Table 1.

The control sample (peeled) had higher ash content compared to the market-processed samples. This difference could be attributed to purity in the control samples and differences in processing. This is consistent with the findings of Abubakar *et al.* (2019), who observed greater ash content in peeled ginger compared to unpeeled ginger. Overall, the ash content in the spices did not exceed the maximum limits mentioned by the European Spice Association for whole ginger, which is 8% (ESA, 2018). Ash content serves as a quality indicator for detecting potential adulteration and assessing the overall purity by reflecting the mineral composition of food, with higher values indicating a greater concentration of essential minerals, while lower values suggest a reduced mineral content (Abubakar *et al.*, 2019).

Table 1: Percentage Moisture and Total Ash Content

Parameters	Kawo Market	Unguwar Rimi Market	Central Market	Control (Peeled)	Control (Unpeeled)	Mean±SD (%)
Moisture	5.21 ^c	4.82 ^b	5.16 ^c	3.82 ^a	4.25 ^a	4.65 ^b ±0.6
Total Ash	4.27 ^a	4.60 ^b	4.43 ^a	4.89 ^c	4.61 ^b	4.56 ^b ±0.2

Values are given as percentage. In each row, values with different superscripts are statistically different ($p < 0.01$, 99 % Confidence limit)

3.2 Total Aflatoxin Concentration

The overall aflatoxin concentration ranged from 0.153-0.274 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$. The highest concentration was recorded for the Central market at 0.274 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ while the lowest was recorded for Unguwar Rimi market at 0.153 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$. A significant difference in the levels of aflatoxins between the two controls, whereby aflatoxin levels in unpeeled were higher than in peeled gingers as shown in Figure 1.

The low aflatoxin concentration in ginger may be as a result of the antifungal protein in ginger rhizomes, and this protein had a strong antifungal activity toward various fungi (Bulent and Alan, 2015). The low moisture content recorded also hinders the growth of spoilage microorganisms (Abu *et al.*, 2023). The control

samples exhibited significantly lower aflatoxin levels compared to the market-processed sample. This suggests that the samples might have been exposed to fungal contamination during pre-harvesting period, processing and prolonged storage or handling. The difference observed between the two controls indicated that the highest levels of aflatoxin contamination were found in ginger peels, and this is in line with the work reported by Makundi *et al.* (2024) who also recorded highest levels of aflatoxin in whole ginger compared to peeled ginger. Despite the presence of aflatoxins, all samples remained well below the EU/WHO/NAFDAC regulatory limit of 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ (Wakhungu *et al.*, 2021).

Figure 1: Aflatoxin Concentration in the Collected Ginger Samples

3.3 Detection of Adulteration in Ginger

3.3.1 Physical Characteristics

The peeled control had a strong and pungent odour, lighter yellow colour and finer texture with no visible particles, while the unpeeled control sample had a pungent and earthy odour, slightly darker yellow colour and a slightly coarse texture. The three market-processed samples exhibited less intense pungency, varying shades of brown and inconsistent textures with visible particles (Table 2 and Plate 1).

The control samples of ginger exhibited finer textures and more vibrant and uniform colours, likely due to the controlled processing while the market-processed samples showed inconsistent textures and varied coloration, suggesting differing handling and storage conditions. The more uniform and vibrant appearance of the controls could indicate higher quality and freshness. The variations in physical attributes were presumed to be due to changes in different processing methods and possible adulteration with other flours (Amponsah *et al.*, 2022).

Table 2: Physical Characteristics of Ginger

Spice/Sample	Odour	Colour	Texture	Appearance
Ginger/Control (Peeled)	Strong, fresh scent	Yellow	Fine, smooth	Uniform, no visible particles
Ginger/Control (Unpeeled)	Earthy, Pungent	Light brown	Slightly coarse	Fibrous granules
Ginger/Kawo Market	Off ginger scent	Dark brown	Slightly coarse	Non-uniform, visible particles
Ginger/Unguar Rimi Market	Less pungent	Dark brown	Smooth	Non-uniform, visible particles
Ginger/Central Market	Pungent	Brown	Coarse	Uniform, visible particles

Plate 1: Powdered Ginger of Controls (Peeled and Unpeeled) and Market-Processed Samples

3.3.2 FTIR Data Obtained for Powdered Ginger

The FTIR spectra of the controls (peeled and unpeeled) and the three market-processed ginger samples showed variations in several key absorption regions (Table 3). A broad absorption band between 3200–3600 cm^{-1} , associated with O–H stretching, was observed across all samples. However, the intensity was lower in the market-processed samples compared to the controls (Figures 2 and 3). In the C–H stretching region (2800–3000 cm^{-1}), all samples exhibited absorption bands typical of aliphatic hydrocarbons, though a slight shift and reduced intensity were noted in the market-processed ginger. The C=O stretching region (1650–1750 cm^{-1}) showed stronger absorption in the market-processed samples than in the peeled and unpeeled controls (Figures 2 and 3). The C–O and C–N vibration region (1000–1300 cm^{-1}) also presented broader peaks in the market-processed samples. In the fingerprint region (1500–500 cm^{-1}), additional peaks and intensity differences were observed in the market-processed samples that were not present in the control spectra (Figures 2 and 3). When compared to the spectra of possible adulterants (maize flour and alligator pepper), similarities were observed (Figure 4). In the 3200–3600 cm^{-1} region, both selected adulterants exhibited distinctive patterns similar to those in the market-processed samples. The C–H stretching (2800–3000 cm^{-1}) and C=O stretching (1650–1750 cm^{-1}) regions of maize flour closely aligned with those of the market-

processed ginger. Similarly, the 1000–1300 cm^{-1} regions showed intense and broad peaks in maize flour, nearly identical to those seen in the market-processed ginger samples (Figure 4). The fingerprint region (1500–500 cm^{-1}) also showed overlaps between the market-processed ginger and alligator pepper (Figure 4), with peaks that were absent in both peeled and unpeeled controls (Figures 2 and 3).

The control ginger samples (peeled and unpeeled) exhibited stronger O–H stretching bands indicating higher levels of natural bioactive compounds such as gingerols and shogaols. In contrast, reduced O–H intensity in the market-processed samples suggests degradation of these compounds (Anagaw *et al.*, 2024). This finding aligns with Amponsah *et al.* (2022), who observed similar trends in powdered ginger samples. The spectral similarity between the market-processed samples and maize flour in this region supports the likelihood of starch-based adulteration, consistent with findings by Madhuri *et al.* (2021). All samples showed C–H stretching typical of lipids and organic matter. However, enhanced C=O absorption in the market-processed samples suggests the presence of carbohydrate fillers like maize flour (Lohumi *et al.* 2014). Notable differences in the fingerprint region, including new peaks and intensity shifts, further support adulteration. These changes closely matched spectra of maize flour, implying the addition of these substances to increase bulk (Yu *et al.*, 2022). The spectral

overlap between the market-processed samples and alligator pepper, particularly in the fingerprint region, points to its possible use as an adulterant, while alligator pepper is more expensive than ginger, its presence may result from cross-contamination during grinding, or intentionally to enhance pungency, aroma, or perceived medicinal value. This highlights the complex nature of spice adulteration.

Daszykowski *et al.* (2023) reported similar trends, where alternative plant ingredients are used to mimic flavor characteristics, such as the addition of capsaicin-rich materials to ginger. Since distinct molecular structures of adulterants alter the fingerprint region, these findings align with previous studies on food adulteration detection via FTIR spectroscopy (Galvin-King *et al.*, 2020).

Figure 2: Overlapped FTIR Spectra of Ginger (Peeled Control vs. Market-Processed Samples)

Figure 3: Overlapped FTIR Spectra of Ginger (Unpeeled Control vs. Market-Processed Samples)

Figure 4: Overlapped FTIR Spectra of Ginger (Market-Processed Samples vs. Possible Adulterants)

Table 3: Functional Groups of FTIR absorption bands

Wavenumber (cm ⁻¹)	Functional Group	Band Assignment
3200-3600	O-H Stretch	Hydrogen-bonded hydroxyl group
2800-3000	C-H Stretch	Aliphatic hydrocarbons (Lipids)
1650-1750	C=O Stretch	Ester carbonyl groups (lipids)
1000-1300	C-O / C-N Stretch	Starch, alcohol, ethers, amines, protein
1500-500	Fingerprint region	Unique spectral fingerprint

Sari *et al.*, 2025

4.0 CONCLUSION

The moisture content value of the market-processed ginger sample was significantly higher than the controls but overall, still low, thereby enhancing its shelf life. The presence of ash content is an indication of the level of minerals and organic matter present in the ginger samples; therefore, it can be an important source of minerals. The aflatoxin levels fall

within the accepted limit EU/WHO/NAFDAC regulatory limit of 10µg/kg indicating that this ginger samples are safe for consumption based on aflatoxin levels. FTIR analysis confirmed the presence of starch-based and other plant-based adulterants such as maize flour and alligator pepper in the market-processed samples, indicating intentional adulteration and undisclosed ingredients. This compromises the

nutritional and medicinal properties of these spices, reducing their purity and therapeutic potential.

RECOMMENDATIONS

There is a need to strengthen food safety monitoring by empowering state and local-level regulatory agencies to collaborate with national bodies. This will help bridge the gap between federal oversight and local practices, especially in informal markets.

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